

METHODS OF LEARNING PHRASAL VERBS IN EFFECTIVE WAYS

Salomova Sevara Choriyeвна
student of Termez State University

Abstract

In this article, we can get information about learning English phrasal verbs in other languages in our republic and processes related to teaching, the ability to memorize new words of students taking into account the ways to successfully and effectively organize the study of new phrasal verbs.

Key words: phrasal verb, correct translation, lexical phenomena, teaching methodology

What is a phrasal verb? A phrasal verb is a verb combined with a preposition or adverb (or both) that means something different from each of the words that make up the verb.

There are many different ways to teach English phrasal verbs to learners :

- *Teach the construction of a phrasal verb*

Start with the basic definition and construction of phrasal verbs so your students can get a baseline. A phrasal verb is a combination of 2 words, usually a verb and a preposition, that create a phrase with a different meaning. The entire phrase acts as the verb in the sentence.

- *Identify when a verb and preposition combination is not a phrasal verb*

Not all verb and preposition combinations are phrasal verbs. For a phrase to be a phrasal verb, it must have an entirely new meaning from the 2 words separately. Have your students test word combinations to see if they are phrasal verbs. If the phrase has a different meaning than the 2 words individually, then it is a phrasal verb.

- *Explain the difference between separable and inseparable phrasal verbs*

Some phrasal verbs can have a direct object in between their verb and prepositions. This means they are separable. Inseparable phrasal verbs must stay together or they won't make sense. The only way to tell if on is separable or inseparable is by trying the sentence both ways and seeing if they both make sense.

- Introduce a small list of phrasal verbs every day

Don't overwhelm your students with long lists of words that they have to memorize. When you start teaching phrasal verbs, introduce them slowly. Try starting each class with a list of 5-10 phrasal verbs and reviewing their meanings. This way, the students gradually build up a list of phrasal verbs without getting overwhelmed.

- Organize phrasal verbs into categories

Since there are so many phrasal verbs, grouping similar ones together can help students learn better. People learn better with patterns than with random selections. Picking out groups of phrasal verbs that begin with the same word, for example, is a good way to organize the phrases.

- Teach students how to figure out verbs using context clues

There are over 2,000 phrasal verbs in English, so it's not possible for them to memorize each one. Rather than having students memorize lists of words, teach them how to identify phrasal verbs from sentence context clues. Show them a sentence and circle the phrasal verb. Ask them to give you a definition of the verb based on its use in the sentence. Help the students along by asking questions, but let them figure out the definition. This helps them learn better.

- Have your students to look up phrasal verbs in the dictionary

If students are confused or lost and can't figure out if a word is a phrasal verb, they can look it up in the dictionary. Phrasal verbs come after the singular verb in the dictionary. Let them use dictionaries when they're first learning phrasal verbs to help them if they get stuck.

It is impossible to guess the meaning of a phrasal verb on sense of the main verb, as a rule. What does "put down" mean? To put down? At all not. If not to foreknow, well you won't guess in any way that "to criticize" it. I hate my boss putting me down all the time. – It isn't pleasant to me that my boss constantly criticizes me.

When training in the phonetic, grammatical and lexical phenomena of a foreign language first of all their comparison to the similar phenomena of the native language, detection of their similarities and distinctions is necessary. Only by such comparison it is possible to train in a correct translation of this or that training material. Ignoring of the grammatical phenomena and a lexical system of the native language not effectively and, in effect, is useless as the native language influences creation of thoughts and statements of trainees in a foreign language and certainly helps digestion of new language material. One of ways of training in the grammatical and lexical phenomena of a foreign language is the translation.

Phrasal verbs very often have idiomatic value, i.e. are used metaphorically. For example, the dog dug up a bone. The dog has dug out a bone. We dug up some interesting facts. We have grubbed up the interesting facts. In English, as well as in many other languages, pretexts and adverbs make a certain sense. For example: up – means the movement up, down – down, Therefore, to turn the music up is translated how to lift a sound, and to turn down – to muffle, lower. At the metaphorical use of up – means increase in a size, quantity, force, and down – reduction. Thus, these sentences can be translated as follows: The prices went up – the prices povysilis. the children quietened down – children have become silent (have calmed down). In Russian, some phrasal verbs can find equivalents, using a verb with different prefixes: Drive to – to go, Drive into – to drive, Drive up – to approach, Drive off – to drive off Thus, when training

in phrasal verbs and ways of their translation use of Russian yields considerable results. Trainees, understanding an essence of a phrasal verb by means of an equivalent in Russian, logically correctly select the word, necessary on sense, in the native language. Phrasal verbs are rather often used in sports terminology. to warm up – to warm muscles before training or competition, to cool down – after training or competition at - to drive muscles in a normal state, to join in – to participate in sporting events, games, to drop out – to leave competitions or race, etc. Some of them have strongly entered Russian and in Armenian languages as the sports term, such as: Knock down – falling in boxing after blow, to knock smb. out, to bring someone to an unconsciousness, to bring the opponent out of further competitions (having won against him). When training in phrasal verbs it is possible to offer trainees learning them by heart. At such approach the purpose of training in phrasal verbs – understanding and the correct use – can't be reached fully. It is much more effective to offer trainees logical approach to the translation of phrasal verbs according to their contextual value. [26, p. 326]

Phrasal verbs can have several different meanings, which are very different from each other:

Pick up a bag up off the floor – to lift a bag from a floor;

Pick up the trail – to find a trace;

Pick up a chick – to pick up the little girl (slang).

Difficulty the third:

Some grammatical difficulties are connected with phrasal verbs, for example there are divided phrasal verbs and not divided. On any external signs it is impossible to understand what verbs divided what aren't present — it need to be spotted in the textbook, the dictionary or an example from the text. In the divided phrasal verbs after the main verb it is possible to squeeze addition: Plug in the kettle, please. – Plug the kettle in, please. In not divided it isn't allowed. He ran through his report once more. – He ran his report through once more. Phrasal verbs are one of the most difficult aspects for learners of the English language. In many cases the meaning of the phrasal verb cannot be deduced from its elements, i.e., it is being used idiomatically. For example: a learner who knows that to tick is to make a checkmark may have difficulty in understanding the sentence The teacher ticked off the student for being late, in which the phrasal verb to tick off means to reprimand or to express disapproval. Many phrasal verbs are polysemous; i.e., they have more than one meaning. The phrasal verb to put down has the literal meaning of putting something down on the table or floor.

It is not mandatory to use phrasal verbs while learning English. But those who want to learn the language in depth should definitely try to learn every aspect of this language. It benefits both young and old people alike. It is effective to try different methods for this

REFERENCES

1. Hunston S. Corpora in Applied Linguistics, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2002. – 161 p.
2. Kodukhov V.I. Introduction to linguistics. M., 1987 .- 289 p.

3. Labov W. The Social Stratification of English in New York City. Washington, D.C., Center for Applied Linguistics, 1966. – 127 p.
4. Mechkovskaya N.B. General linguistics. Structural and social typology of languages. - 2nd ed. - M.: Flinta, Nauka, 2010.
5. Ikramovna, I. D. (2020). Using interactive training aids foreign languages at university. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR), 9(3), 92-95.
5. Z. Ibodullayeva. The main directions of developing students' speech in native language classes. 85-92, 2023
6. Z. Ibodullayeva. Use of methods in teaching the topic of case. 391-395, 2023.
7. Z.D. Anvarovna. Yevropa ta'lim fanlaridagi tadqiqot va mulohaza jurnali. Axborotlashtirish sharoitida oliy ta'lim talabalari uchun "Ta'limda axborot texnologiyalari" mavzusidagi ma'ruzalar uchun. 7-jild, 2019-yil.
8. Anvarovna, Z. D. (2023). APPROACHES TO THE STUDY OF SPEECH VERBS IN MODERN ENGLISH. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(5), 457-466.
9. Ziyoyeva, D. A. (2023). SEMANTICS OF THE SPEECH VERBS SPEAK, TALK IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(6), 217–225. Retrieved from <https://openidea.uz/index.php/idea/article/view/912>
10. Anvarovna, Z. D. (2023). The Classification of Speech Verbs in English. Miasto Przyszłości, 33, 268-274.
11. Ziyoyeva, D. A. (2023). SEMANTICS OF THE SPEECH VERBS SPEAK, TALK IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(6), 217-225.
12. Зиёева, Д. А. (2020). Синтаксические характеристики глаголов английской речи. Молодой ученый, (23), 695-698.
13. Anvarovna, Z. D. Different meaning of the speech verbs say, tell, speak, talk. International Journal on Integrated Education, 3(1), 95-97.

14. Samadov, B. S., Jalilova, F. S., Ziyaeva, D. A., Sharipova, D. S., Ozodova, N. X., Norova, H. U., ... & Kudina, O. V. (2020). Pharmacological properties and chemical composition “Momordica charantia l”.

15. Samadov, B. S., Jalilova, F. S., Ziyaeva, D. A., Sharipova, D. S., Ozodova, N. X., Norova, H. U., ... & Kudina, O. V. (2020). Pharmacological properties and chemical composition “Momordica charantia l”.